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To the Question of Defining Place and Distribution of the Final Syntaxeme in the Structure of the English Sentence

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***Abstract:** This article analyzes the issue of studying syntactic semantics of the sentence as well as the role and distribution of the final syntaxemes in the sentence structure. Also, attention is paid to determining the valence of final syntaxemes in simple and compound sentences in English. The article covers important theoretical and practical issues in linguistics within the framework of the topic.*

***Key words:** syntactic semantics, final syntaxeme, distribution, simple and compound sentences, syntactic analysis.*

Introduction

It is recognized that the issue of studying the syntactic semantics of a sentence is carried out so far within the framework of the concept of forming lexical meanings based on word forms. But the opinions of linguists differ from each other regarding the definition given to the meaning of this term in grammar textbooks.

Since the science of linguistics is considered a social phenomenon, theories and views in language change. In particular, during the detailed study of the issue of syntactic analysis, we can see that English and American linguists approached this analysis differently.

Literature Analysis

Representatives of the American school of structural linguistics studied grammar on a formalistic basis. Their experiences made it necessary to pay attention to semantics at the syntactic level. Using chain analysis, Z.S.Harris puts forward the idea of dividing sentence structure into elementary sentence

fragments and adjuncts based on the distributive method.¹ L.E.Longacre follows him and uses the chain analysis method, dividing the sentence directly into its participants.²

The syntactic analysis of a sentence is limited to the analysis of direct participants using the chain method. Therefore, this method of analysis is limited to the morphological characteristics of the units included in the structure of the sentence and cannot proceed to the process of synthesis. Finally, after the emergence of transformed grammar, the method of analyzing syntactic units in a sentence by dividing them into segments and using distributive methods was created and developed.

In America and England, the significant work was carried out by such representatives of this direction as N.Chomsky, P.Roberts, E.Bach, A.Hathaway, P.S.Rosenbaum, K.Olaf, Z.Hedde and others.³ These linguistic analysis methods were improved and new aspects were discovered according to new researches and the demands of the times.

Methodology

In the study of grammatical features based on such methods as distributional, transformational, tagmeme, and chain analysis, linguists, including A.I.Smirnitsky, carried out significant work that deserves attention.⁴ In this article, based on syntactic connections, the valency of syntactic units in the structure of a sentence expressing a goal is determined, and attention is also paid to determining their differential syntactic, differential syntactic-semantic features and the possibilities of combining them with other syntaxemes based on specific syntactic connections.

When analyzed dividing into components, syntactic elements form the external structure of sentences. And when analyzed by dividing them into syntaxemes, the internal structure of sentences is covered.

Distinguishing between surface and deep structures of a sentence, linguists try to analyze them using different transformation methods: if “deep structure” means the sentence variant “The boy is sleeping”, then “surface structure” means the form of the question “Is the boy sleeping?”.⁵ In such an analysis, the formal aspects of the sentence are taken into account, and the analysis is limited to dividing them directly into participants.

The purpose of this research is to analyze the syntactic units of the external structure of the sentence, their mutual syntactic connections and differential syntactic features by means of modeling methods; it consists of determining the semantics of the syntactic units in the internal structure of the sentence at the syntactic level.

Research Methods

In researching this issue, the effective use of the linguistic methods created by A.M.Mukhin, as well as a number of other scientific studies, brought positive results.⁶ Relying on this method of linguistic

¹ Harris Z.S. String Analysis of Sentence Structure.– The Hague, 1964.-358 p.

² Longacre R.E. String Constituent Analysis. Language, 1960. – V36.–№1– P.163-189.

³ Chomsky N. Syntactic Structures. 2-nd edition. Berlin – New York: MOUTON de Gruyter, 2002. – 118p.; Roberts P. English Syntax.–New York, 1964.-414p.; Bach E. An introduction to transformational grammar. – New-York, 1964.-284p.; Hathway V.A. Transformational Syntax. The Grammar of Modern American English.– New-York, 1967.-421p.; Rosenbaum P.S. The Grammar of English Predicate Complement Constructions.– Cambridge, Mass: The M.I.T. Press, 1967.-278p.; Olaf K., Hedde Z. Introducing Syntax. Cambridge University Press, 2017.-226 p.

⁴ Смирницкий А.И. Синтаксис английского языка. – Москва: Лит. на иностр. яз., 1957. – С. 8-23 (286с)

⁵ en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Deep_structure_and_surface_structure.

⁶ Мухин А.М. Структура предложений и их модели. – Ленинград, Ленинград отд.: Наука, 1968.-230с.; Мухин А.М. Синтаксемный анализ и проблема уровней языка.– Ленинград: Наука, 1980.-304с.; Мухин А.М. Функциональный синтаксис. Функциональная лексикология. Функциональная морфология.– СПб., 2007.-198с

analysis, the syntactic units expressing aim in the simple and compound sentence structures of the English language are determined on the basis of syntactic relations.

When analyzing by dividing into syntaxemes, the final syntactic units in the sentences that are the object of the study are compared with other sentences that have units that realize the goal. It has been recognized that this kind of approach to sentence analysis has yielded positive results in some scientific studies.

Place of final syntaxemes

In English, final syntaxemes can occur in different places in the sentence structure. In many cases it is observed that in a sentence final syntaxemes follow causative syntaxemes. All syntaxemes variants within substantiality, processuality and qualificativity are observed in this position:

1. on the basis of substantiality:

My parents used to move to Zomin for the summer because of their health condition.

2. on the basis of processuality:

I dont want to take part in this ceremony, lest someone would recognize me and be aware of my stay in the town.

3. on the basis of qualificativity:

He took some warm clothes with him in order not to get cold during his holiday in the North.

The final syntaxeme in the substantial base has the form of a phrase with the preposition *for* at the end of the sentence. In this case it can express final actional, final objective or final stative syntaxemes:

We stopped by the road for a rest.

I have done it for my mother.

In the scope of processuality, final syntaxemes at the end of the sentence are mainly expressed by intransitive verbs. If expressed by transitive verbs, the substantial object syntaxeme is required after the final syntaxeme:

I regularly go to the gym to practice.

She hurried into her room to get dressed.

He entered the kitchen to have something to eat.

On the background of processuality, it is observed that passive final syntaxemes mainly appear at the end of a sentence, and there are also cases when they occur at the beginning of a sentence in the function of a detached part of a sentence:

I have just sent my article to be edited.

We are going to hang the poster higher to be clearly seen.

On the basis of qualificativity, the use of final syntaxemes at the end of a sentence is mainly observed with stative final and qualitative final syntaxemes, where these units are expressed by a linking verb and an adjective or participle in the past tense:

He always does his best to be successful.

She enjoyed lying on the white sands of the beach to be suntanned.

He decided to get financial knowledge to be rich.

The use of final syntaxemes at the beginning of a sentence is observed during the logical emphasis of the target state or when it is used in the function of a detached part of a sentence. In this position, final syntaxemes are mainly activated on the basis of qualificativity and processuality:

To keep fit and strong, you should always work out in the gym.

To occupy a suitable seat in the lecture hall, he left his house earlier.

Final syntaxemes in the structure of an English sentence are realized in the functions of a detached part of a sentence, a predicate, an adverbial modifier of purpose, an object, an attribute, a subordinate clause of purpose and time.

Distribution of final syntaxemes

Below we will get acquainted with the distribution of final syntaxemes. Final syntaxemes are most often located between the tense form of a transitive verb and an object:

1. as a nuclear predicative: following non-transitive verb, which is in the Perfect tense, dependent transitive verb of purpose in the infinitive form, expresses an action related to the future tense, and subordinates the substantial object syntaxeme:

Samko, I have come to fetch your daughter. (RJ, 187)

2. as an adverbial modifier of manner: *positive or negative form of an intransitive verb of the present participle + to V_inf_ + possessive pronoun + adjective + noun:*

... old Jew walked on, not troubling to hide his contemptuous smile. (RJ, 220)

3. as a verb in the positive or negative form: *transitive verb of action in the past tense + infinitive form of a transitive verb of purpose + object clause:*

He did not even look to see what he was eating. (RJ, 209)

4. as *intransitive verb in the imperative mood + for N + adverbial modifier of time:*

Come for the letter this evening and then take it right away. (RJ, 236)

5. as *transitive verb in the form of the present tense (has a future tense meaning) + to Vinf + Obj + adverbial clause of purpose:*

I want to save Eva, so that she doesn't have to wear a yellow star. (RJ, 203)

6. as interrogative sentences with the meaning of a request: in the structure of interrogative sentences with the meaning of a request, the distribution of the final syntaxeme consists of the actional and object syntaxemes in the preposition and the temporal syntaxeme in the postposition:

Could I trouble you to go outside for a moment? (RJ, 179)

7. in the *for to Infinitive Construction*: when the final syntaxeme is activated with the *for – to – Infinitive Construction*, the purpose is realized with the help of speech verbs or action verbs, is subordinate to a state verb, and is surrounded by another syntactic constructions:

He waited for her to speak but it seemed that her answer would never come. (PAPT, 146)

8. as a verb of action in the function of a predicate: *verb of action in the function of a predicate + locative syntaxeme + manner syntaxeme + final syntaxeme + attributive clause*. The final syntaxeme in such a distribution is expressed in the form *for + Noun/Prn*:

He looked round the room in vain for some whom he knew. (RJ, 176)

9. at the beginning of a sentence in the function of a detached part of a sentence: in this case it is surrounded by manner and interrogative syntaxemes:
Anxious to see whether they would understand him, he stretched out his arms to the full width of the table. (RJ, 176)
10. as part of complex syntactic constructions: in this position it is located after the conjunction as part of a complex subordinate clause:
You are very thoughtful, said Haso, praising him, and to show his gratitude he completely opened his heart to him. (RJ, 143)
11. as part of *Parallel Construction*:
How she had tried to convince him, how she had raised her voice to emphasize it! (RJ, 118)
12. when a question is asked to the adverbial modifier of purpose: in this case, other parts of the sentence are placed between the interrogative pronoun and the preposition *for*:
What are you still standing there for? (RJ, 244)
13. when the final syntaxeme is expressed with *to make sure*: it can be followed by object clause in the affirmative, interrogative or negative meaning, expressing an action or state in the future:
I am telling you this to make sure that we understand one another in the future. (RJ, 153)
14. it can be found as part of object clause with the omitted conjunction: *be going + infinitive + object*:
Brother Haso had told them they were going to make history. (RJ, 237)
15. also we can find the following distribution: *transitive verb + object + adverbial modifier of manner + adverbial modifier of purpose + object*:
The cold blue eyes studied him impersonally not to miss anything and then settled on his face. (PAPT, 76)

If the final syntaxemes is expressed by the verb *to miss* (*пропустить*), it is always in the negative form. Also, the distribution mentioned above is observed with intransitive verb:

Slowly he flicked the pages over, pausing occasionally to read an entry here and there. (PAPT, 92)

Conclusions

While studying the place and distribution of final syntaxemes in the sentence structure, we observed the occurrence of them at the beginning, middle and end of the sentence. When the final syntaxeme is at the beginning of a sentence it occurs on the basis of processuality as part of a detached part of a sentence. In the middle of the sentence, there are observed processual final, substantial final and qualificative final syntaxemes expressed by a transitive verb. At the end of a sentence we can see mainly substantial final syntaxemes.

If we draw conclusions about the distribution of final syntaxemes, they are mainly surrounded by object and actional syntaxemes. They are also connected with manner, attributive, causative syntaxemes; they are found in affirmative, interrogative, imperative sentences, parallel constructions, rhetorical interrogative sentences.

References:

1. Bach E. An introduction to transformational grammar. New-York, 1964. - 284 p.
2. Chomsky N. Syntactic Structures. 2-nd edition. Berlin New York: MOUTON de Gruyter, 2002. 118 p.

3. en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Deep_structure_and_surface_structure.
4. Harris Z.S. String Analysis of Sentence Structure.– The Hague, 1964.-358 p.
5. Hathway V.A. Transformational Syntax. The Grammar of Modern American English.– New-York, 1967.-421p.
6. Longacre R.E. String Constituent Analysis. Language, 1960. – V36.–№1– P.163-189.
7. Olaf K., Hedde Z. Introducing Syntax. Cambridge University Press, 2017.-226 p.
8. Roberts P. English Syntax.– New York, 1964.-414p.
9. Rosenbaum P.S. The Grammar of English Predicate Complement Constructions.– Cambridge, Mass: The M.I.T. Press, 1967.-278p.
10. Мухин А.М. Структура предложений и их модели. – Ленинград, Ленинград отд.: Наука, 1968.-230с.
11. Мухин А.М. Функциональный синтаксис. Функциональная лексикология. Функциональная морфология. – СПб., 2007.-198с.
12. Мухин А.М. Синтаксемный анализ и проблема уровней языка.– Ленинград: Наука, 1980.-304с.
13. Смирницкий А.И. Синтаксис английского языка. – Москва: Лит. на иностр. яз., 1957. – 286с.